

A palaeogravity calculation for the gigantic fossil arthropod *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*)

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Abstract

One fundamental technique to quantify palaeogravity is to compare dynamically similar extinct and extant animals. This technique is applied to a fossil trackway of the gigantic fossil arthropod *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*). The results indicate a tentative palaeogravity of about 0.37g for 330 Ma.

Key words: Palaeogravity, *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*).

Martin Whyte (2005) reported the discovery of a complex fossil trackway in Carboniferous age fossil deposits in Scotland (see figure 1). It was made roughly 330 million years ago by a huge, six-legged water scorpion that was about 1.6 m long and a metre wide. This was believed to be the largest terrestrial trackway of a walking arthropod found so far (0.2 m wider than any other trackway of this type), as well as the first record of locomotion on land for a species of *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*). This evidence of lumbering movement indicated that these giant arthropods, now extinct, could survive out of water at a time when the earliest tetrapods were making their transition to the land. The trackway was exposed on a bedding plane close to the base of a sandstone section in a non-marine sequence. It is 6 m long, 0.90–0.98 m wide and consists of sinuous, paired belts of appendage prints flanking a sub-central groove. The animal appeared to be slowly crawling across the ground, while in places the footprints have been erased by the central groove, which was made by the posterior part of the animal being

dragged behind it. An occasional oblique lineation on the sides and base of the groove indicated that the motion was jerky. The slow, stilted progression, together with the dragging of the posterior, indicated that the animal was not buoyant but moving across land. The pattern and character of the limb prints was identified as being most consistent with the relatively short-limbed *Hibbertopterus*. The trackway maker would have been comparable in size to the largest known hibbertopteroid body fossils, which have head shields 0.65 m wide.

The mechanical stress imposed on such a large arthropod seems to imply that it would struggle to walk on land. As size increases, the volume and weight of an arthropod would be cubed while the leg area and strength would only be squared. This means the arthropod must reach a maximum size limit when its legs wouldn't be able to support its mass. In order to try to assess if it was possible for such large arthropods to walk on land Dalingwater (1985) used the extant *Limulus*, a horseshoe crab, as

Figure 1. Photograph of a track identified as a short-limbed *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*) by Whyte (2005), complete with an enlarged section. The track is the long curved line stretching from left to right, just above the geological hammer, with additional marks on the two sides of the curved line. Note that the sandstone bed is dipping at 45 degrees away from the viewer. The original photograph is available from Wikipedia Commons (see reference).

Figure 2. A modern day horseshoe crab trackway, with an enlarged section. Note the claw markings, tail drag and wandering path and its similarity with the *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*) trackway. The original photograph is available from Wikipedia Commons (see reference).

Figure 3. The *Hibbertopterus* (*Eurypterida*) drawn to scale (on the left) compared with the calculated size of a horseshoe crab in a palaeogravity of 0.37g (on the right), assuming the horseshoe crab continued to have the same dynamic capabilities. Both trackways are 0.95 m wide. The horseshoe crab has a large protective shield covering most of its legs and head. If this shield is ignored its legs and body would be similar to an ancient sea scorpion and it would leave similar trackways. The *Hibbertopterus* is redrawn after Tetlie (2007); the horseshoe crab is redrawn after Holder (1892).

a model. These arthropods are the closest living relatives to the extinct water scorpions. Although horseshoe crabs are primarily aquatic animals they are also capable of excursions onto land. Calculations based on them implied that, if the animal maintained dynamic similarity, the cuticles of the legs would become too thick to leave sufficient space for muscles within the limbs of a large animal. Thus the horseshoe crab is about as large as we might expect such an animal to grow. Briggs *et al* (1991) noted that larger arthropods would need some method to offset potentially unacceptable stresses on their limbs, for example by changes in shape or in skeletal materials, or by a reduction in locomotor performance. On theoretical grounds, an arthropod with a body length of around 1.6 m would not be able to move about as freely as this fossil trackway indicates.

The large arthropods would be able to move freely on land if palaeogravity was less at that time. Assuming that the *Hibbertopterus* recorded in the fossil record moved in a dynamically similar way to an extant *Limulus* we can calculate palaeogravity from:

$$g = Sl / Sh$$

where *Sl* is the relative size of the *Limulus*, and *Sh* is the relative size of *Hibbertopterus*. The derivation of this formula is discussed in detail in Hurrell (2011).

In order to use this formula we need to reassure ourselves that these two animals were moving in dynamically similar ways. The track identified as a short-limbed *Hibbertopterus* (see figure 1) can be compared with a typical track left by a giant horseshoe crab (see figure 2). The claw markings, tail drag and wandering path are similar for both trackways so they did appear to be moving in dynamically similar ways.

Assuming that the *Hibbertopterus* reached its maximum size limit in a reduced gravity, it can be compared with the largest horseshoe crab in a 1g environment. Mainichi (2005) reported finding a giant horseshoe crab measuring 0.795 m from head to tail, with a mass of five kilograms, in the sea near the Kujukushima islands off Sasebo, Nagasaki Prefecture of Japan. The horseshoe crab's shell measured 0.353 m in width. It was handed over to the Saikai Pearl Sea Center aquarium, which conducts studies of the Kujukushima islands. The previous largest giant horseshoe crab confirmed in Japan measured 0.63 m in length and weighed about 3.5 kilograms. The five kilogram size has been taken as the largest size of extant horseshoe crabs.

The horseshoe crab has a large protective shield covering most of its legs and head. If this protective shield is ignored it would be very similar to an an-

cient sea scorpion. Compared with the ancient sea scorpion, its legs appear to move in a similar manner, leaving similar footprints whilst dragging its posterior across the ground. Theoretically, a simple comparison of the widths of the two trackways would provide the two relative sizes needed to calculate palaeogravity. The width of the largest horseshoe crab trackway would be slightly less than the width of its protective shield, at 0.345 m, while the width of the ancient *Hibbertopterus* trackway is about 0.94 m.

Thus:

$$g \approx 0.345 / 0.94 \approx 0.37g$$

This estimate of palaeogravity compares an ancient sea scorpion to a dynamically similar horseshoe crab and so it is probably more accurate than previous palaeogravity estimates for sea scorpions, as given in Hurrell (2012), which compared them to extant scorpions. It would be better to use the new estimate of about 0.37g instead of the older estimate.

Another way to envisage the comparison of dynamically similar extinct and extant arthropods is to scale up the extant horseshoe crab to the size it would be in a reduced gravity of 0.37g, assuming it keeps the same dynamic capabilities as the 1g animal. The two trackways would be the same size, as represented in figure 3.

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